

ICO Project Manager and Entrepreneur.

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Abstract

1. Introduction

What is ICO, What is the difference between selling new industrial products and selling new coins/tokens (ICO) What needs to be prepared prior to start your ICO, What and how you proceed ICO to be succeed.

2. Discussion

As I have been in REAL world, not virtual world, the way I look at crypto is maybe from different viewpoint than crypto people. But to sell new products, industrial products or coins/tokens, basically have to be almost same. For me, preparation for selling new industrial products are more solid, honest, credible and promising. But crypto can be same. I have seen ugly ICO projects too many, so I learned a lot about how you should do. There are still so many scams here in this world, but I realize it does not mean they want to be scam, but as the result of improper preparation, any ICO can be scam.

Author biography

Keiko Yuasa ICO Project Manager and Entrepreneur. Over 20+ years experience as Project Manager/Program Manager in Automotive Industry, involving with the project of GM, Ford, Chrysler, Toyota, Honda and Nissan. Worked in the States for 10+ years, traveled on business worldwide. Specialized to manage various aspects of project management including marketing, business strategy, sales, finance and PR.

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